

POSITION PAPER

FROM KNOWLEDGE GAPS TO INNOVATION: A ROADMAP FOR SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE RESEARCH

Insights from multi-stakeholder consultations

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Aquaculture is at a turning point, with digital innovation, climate adaptation, and sustainability emerging as central drivers of its future. Advancing artificial intelligence, data integration, and sustainable feed solutions can greatly enhance productivity, animal welfare, and environmental performance. At the same time, the sector must confront growing climate risks, ensure fair access to innovation, and strengthen resilience among small producers.

Targeted research investment is essential to bridge science and practice, linking digitalization, animal health, resource efficiency, and market understanding into a coherent strategy for sustainable growth.

1. DIGITALIZATION AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The digital transformation of aquaculture offers major opportunities to enhance productivity, sustainability, and food safety. Artificial intelligence (AI), sensors, and the Internet of Things enable real-time monitoring, predictive management, and improved traceability and welfare. Yet, progress is constrained by limited data access, concentration of innovation among large firms, and unresolved cybersecurity and environmental challenges.

RESEARCH NEEDS:

- Advance computer vision, machine learning, and non-invasive sensor technologies to improve predictive models for aquaculture monitoring, linking environmental factors to growth, disease, and climate-related risks, and enabling early mitigation strategies for animal welfare.
- Establish open data policies and interoperability frameworks to facilitate the scaling of AI tools from pilot studies to real-world aquaculture systems.
- Adopt funding models that ensure inclusive and independent AI development, providing equitable access for SMEs and local producers, while supporting animal welfare.
- Develop strategies to strengthen cybersecurity and reduce the environmental footprint of AI systems, including energy and water use in data centres.

2. CLIMATE CHANGE AND ENVIRONMENTAL RISKS

Climate change and new environmental risks are major threats to aquaculture and global food security. Rising temperatures, acidification, extreme events, and hypoxia endanger farmed species and promote diseases that compromise water quality and food safety. At the same time, emerging hazards such as microplastics, antibiotic residues, toxins, and pathogens pose growing risks to both aquatic organisms and consumers, underscoring the urgent need for research to safeguard sustainable production.

RESEARCH NEEDS:

- Investigate the effects of extreme events such as heatwaves on animal health and disease outbreaks and develop predictive alerts to support prompt mitigation measures.

- Assess the impacts of insufficient urban wastewater treatment on aquatic animal health, particularly on bivalve farming, and develop strategies to mitigate associated risks.
- Invest in monitoring and mitigation strategies for biofouling and accessory fauna, considering the increased pressures from climate change and international trade.

3. SUSTAINABLE FEEDS, NUTRITION, AND RESOURCE EFFICIENCY

Sustainable aquaculture depends on nutritious, cost-effective feeds and responsible management of by-products and waste. Key knowledge gaps remain regarding the palatability, metabolism, and nutritional or toxicological effects of alternative ingredients, including plant proteins, algae, and agro-industrial by-products. Limited investment in functional feeds risks foster the reliance on traditional fish-based formulations. At the same time, opportunities exist to enhance sustainability, circularity, and food safety by valorising by-products, promoting zero-waste approaches, and developing feeds that benefit both animal and human nutrition.

RESEARCH NEEDS:

- Species-specific studies on the palatability and nutritional utilization of new feed formulations to ensure optimal growth, quality, health, and welfare of farmed species.
- Bioprospecting new ingredients and bioactive compounds, including pigments, algae, and agro-industrial by-products, assessing their nutritional and toxicological impacts.
- Develop methods to define, assess, and validate feed “functionality” to guide formulation and regulatory evaluation.
- Explore feed formulations that enhance the value of aquaculture products, targeting deficiencies in specific population segments and improving organoleptic characteristics.
- Investigate the use of alternative raw materials to reduce the dependence on fishmeal and fish oil and to promote the valorisation of by-products for new products in food, feed, or nutraceutical applications.
- Develop technologies to precisely quantify biomass and create systems to valorise by-products, enhancing the economic and environmental sustainability of aquaculture.

4. ANIMAL HEALTH, WELFARE, AND GENETIC IMPROVEMENT

Ensuring the health, welfare, and resilience of farmed aquatic species is critical for sustainable and productive aquaculture. Disease outbreaks, stress, and suboptimal handling not only compromise animal welfare but also reduce growth, product quality, and food safety. Climate change and emerging pathogens further exacerbate these risks, requiring innovative approaches to monitoring, prevention, and species adaptation.

RESEARCH NEEDS:

- Develop prophylactic feeding strategies and vaccines with oral administration to reduce stress from handling and avoid chronic inflammation caused by injectable vaccines.
- Identify new indicators of animal welfare and develop environmental sensors and biomarkers, such as stress-related metabolites and proteins to predict and prevent disease.
- Develop enrichment solutions that promote natural behaviours without compromising production efficiency.
- Advance genetic selection protocols for species with increased resistance to diseases and environmental stressors, including climate change.
- Innovate more effective and welfare-conscious stunning and slaughter methods that are cost effective for producers.
- Engage the industry in research on emerging pathogens, such as *Lactococcus*, to strengthen early detection, mitigation, and applied solutions for disease prevention.

5. GOVERNANCE, CAPACITY BUILDING, AND KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

The Portuguese aquaculture sector includes both large enterprises and family-run producers, each with distinct challenges. To ensure effective and inclusive innovation, applied research, skills development, and knowledge exchange are essential. Researchers need direct insight into production, while producers require training in modern technologies, sustainability, and animal welfare. Public education is also critical to foster understanding and acceptance of national aquaculture products.

RESEARCH NEEDS:

- Adapt research and innovation strategies to the specific needs of large-scale companies and small-scale family producers, engaging local organizations to identify sectoral priorities.
- Facilitate personnel exchanges between academia and industry to improve applied research, encourage dialogue between sectors, and foster practical innovation.
- Projects with higher technology readiness levels should integrate economic assessments.
- Invest in specialized technical and digital training, including AI, animal management, sustainability, and welfare, to strengthen national talent and enhance job quality.
- Develop accessible technologies, training, and advisory programs tailored to small-scale producers to increase resilience and enable adoption of modern tools.

6. MARKET, COMMUNICATION, AND FOOD SECURITY

Limited knowledge of consumption habits, nutritional preferences, sustainability concerns, and market trends can constrain producers' capacity to innovate and adapt. Trade barriers and competition from low-cost imports further complicate the sector's ability to provide safe, high-quality, and affordable products.

RESEARCH NEEDS:

- Study consumer preferences and barriers, nutritional requirements, sustainability concerns, and market trends to inform product development and policy decisions.
- Support research on introducing new species and products in the market to enhance sectoral competitiveness and reduce reliance on traditional markets.
- Fund initiatives that promote national aquaculture, and increase societal awareness of product quality, sustainability, and nutritional benefits.
- Support strategies to address distorted reports and misinformation, ensuring consumers to receive accurate information, fostering trust in national aquaculture products.

CONCLUSION

Achieving a sustainable, competitive, and resilient aquaculture sector requires coordinated investment across science, innovation, and capacity building. Digital technologies, climate adaptation, sustainable feeds, and improved animal welfare offer transformative potential, but remain underexploited without dedicated funding.

By prioritizing open data, equitable access to technology, and skills development, funding agencies can accelerate the sector's transition towards circular, climate-resilient, and welfare-conscious production systems. Investing in these strategic areas will strengthen food security, environmental sustainability, and social inclusion, establishing aquaculture as a key pillar of the sustainable blue economy and a driver of national and European competitiveness.

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